

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15543920

Guidance Counselling and Social Studies Education: Catalyst for Building Effective Citizens for National Development in Nigeria

¹TINJA, Rahamat Maina Ph.D & ²TIJANI, O. Abdulgafar Ph.D

¹Department of Educational Foundations
Faculty of Education
Federal University, Gashua, Yobe State, Nigeria
GSM:08036413988. Email:rmtinja@gmail.com

²School of Secondary Education (Arts and Social Sciences)
Federal College of Education (Technical) Potiskum PMB 1013 Yobe State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This paper discusses Guidance Counselling and Social Studies Education as catalyst for building effective citizens for national development in Nigeria. Nigeria in her democratic experience needs effective citizens who will be committed to value dimensions of citizenship orientation as power, love, integrity, hard work, interdependence and loyalty that has contributed in the building and establishment of the great nations and democracies of the world such as England, France, the United States of America, Canada, Germany and Japan. This therefore underscores the importance of Guidance Counselling and Social Studies education as both disciplines make students to develop their potentials through their understanding of maladjusted behaviours that are inimical to progress and national development at large. The paper is focused on the concept of Guidance and Counselling, concept of Social Studies education, effective citizenship, and so on. The paper also highlights some of the challenges facing Guidance Counselling and Social Studies in Nigeria's schools. Based on the challenges, the paper suggests that government at all levels should employ professional counsellors and Social Studies experts with a view to modifying or reforming students' maladjusted behaviours to make them useful to themselves as basis for their contribution to national development and assist them in making future careers among others suggestions

Keywords: Guidance and Counselling, Social Studies Education and Effective Citizenship

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria is a Democratic society blessed with abundant human and natural resources. Ideally, these resources could be considered plausible for accelerated national growth and development. However, it has been realized that there is a clear distinction between the availability of resources and their effective utilization for development. Considering the forgoing, utilization of resources is largely depends on the effectiveness of human resources as manipulator and key driver of the Nigeria's economy. In this context, Ezegbe and Okam (2013) reflected that Nigeria has regrettably witnessed a clearly unfortunate downward trends of decay from developing to under developing nation and from a third world to a forth world and amongst the poorest nation of the world, despite the abundant human and material resources. In their submission, Okam and Chukwu in Ezegbe et al (2013) recount that Nigeria is plagued by multidimensional problems which are antithetical to peace, problems of socio-economic imbalance, social stability and inequality.

The above exposition is a clear indication that Nigeria in her democratic experience needs effective citizen which in the opinion of Kazi (2012) will be committed to value dimensions of citizenship orientation as power, love, integrity, hard work, interdependence and loyalty that has contributed in the building and establishment of the great nations and democracies of the world such as England, France, the United States of America, Canada, Germany and Japan. This scholar expatiated further that, the above great nations were built by citizens who are positively committed at exploring and employing the value dimensions of citizenship education in bringing about national development through enhancement of social, economic, cultural and political to an enviable height. Based on the above reflection, Nigeria desires citizens who will enhance the values intrinsic in citizenship education as precondition for effective discharge of civic duties and responsibilities. By implication, the development of Nigerian society is hinged on effective citizens who place the love of the nation above their religious and tribal affiliations as well as developing zero tolerance for anti-democratic activities inimical to national development. However, this pre-condition remains a great task that may not be accomplished by a single subject area, rather achievable through partnership across disciplines such as Guidance Counselling and Social Studies Education. The fact that these disciplines are hinged on developing citizens' potentials for national productivity make them apt and occupy a place of pride in the Nigeria's educational edifice. It is against this background that this paper discusses guidance counselling and social studies education as catalyst for building effective citizens for national development in Nigeria.

Concept of Guidance and Counselling

The meaning of guidance is subject to many explanations. While scholars like Shertzer and Stone in Tinja (2010) see guidance as direct, pilot or guide; others like Kolo in North- East Development Commission (2024) see guidance as a form of assistance that involves many activities that will help the individual understand himself or herself more and the problem. Guidance "refers to a more directive, or prescriptive form of assistance". This means that the assistance is based on providing information that enables you to give definite instructions to the person being helped (Akinade in North- East Development Commission, 2024). On the other hand, Counselling is a professional and confidential relationship between a guidance counsellor and a client that is facilitated in order to find a lasting solutions to the challenges of the client that is beyond his or her capacity (Odeniyi and Oyediji, 2014). Similarly, Fakunle (2011) perceived Counselling as a professional assistance offered to an individual by trained counselling psychologist to help the individual solve his/ her developmental and adjustment problems.

In the opinion of Israel in Tinja (2014) Counselling is viewed as the heart of guidance since it provides a form of interaction and a link between client and counsellor. Therefore, in counselling, human beings are helped to properly understand themselves, their environment and the problems that are causing high rate of concern. In the same vein, Tinja (2014) asserted that counselling represents a body of knowledge where adequate information is given to the students for socio-personal, educational and ethical requirements for vocational development. Thus, the need for students to form desirable attitudes and values for personal growth as a base to make positive contributions towards national development constitutes the priority in the field of counselling.

Guidance and counselling is a programme of service to individuals based on their needs and the influence of environmental factors (North-East Development Commission, 2024). Guidance programme for schools students are planned to address the physical, social, vocational and academic difficulties of young students. Guidance and counselling is a life changing and enlightened process of making individual useful to himself and the community as a whole. These inseparable concepts refer to an assistance rendered to the people to enable them realize their potentials maximally for personal and societal development. The guidance and counselling purpose include; assisting individual students, teachers, adults and the society in general in the following ways:

1. To find out and make individuals aware of their basic personal prerequisites, abilities, assets, liabilities and potentialities
2. To provide usable information on vocation and to correct or clarify misinformation.

3. Assess an individual's chances to succeed in the labour market.
4. To create awareness of clients in the availability of jobs and how to progress in it.
5. To make available opportunities for further training and advancement in occupations.
(Kolo in Denga, 2004)

Social Studies Education

Social Studies as a popular school subject is viewed as the study of man in relationship with those variables that makes up both physical and social environment. It is a course of study which deals with the influence of man on his social environment and how environmental factors influence to a greater extent, his decision making process. Social Studies is a discipline that projects social cultural values of the society. Social Studies enables citizens to be socially and morally transformed through life enhancing and supportive skills (Mofoluwawo in Ezekiel, Adegboyega & Omoniyi, 2023). Social Studies education is designed to inculcate worthwhile cultural values and virtues into the learners to enable them live and contribute immensely to national transformation within the democratic governance in Nigeria (Akinola & Tijani, 2022).

Social Studies is perceived this subject area as an organized, integrated study of man and his environment both physical and social, emphasizing on cognition, functional skills and desirable attitudes and actions for the purpose of producing an effective citizenry (Ololobu in Ezekiel, Adegboyega & Omoniyi, 2023). According to Akinola (2018), Social Studies is the holistic process by which an individual acquires intellectual tools and skills to live in the world that is full of opportunities and challenges. Ashikor (2019) defines Social Studies as an integrated approach in the study of the Social Sciences and humanities to promote civic competence. The study drawing upon such disciplines as Anthropology, Archaeology, Economics, Geography, History, Law, Philosophy, Political Science, Psychology, Religion and Sociology, as well as appropriate contents from the humanities, Mathematics and Natural Science.

It is inferred from the above that Social Studies is an important school subject designed to inculcate desirable social attitudes and worthwhile societal values into the learners with a view to make them responsible members of their families and effective citizens of Nigeria. In doing this, the subject area is packaged with the following objectives:

1. To develop capacity to learn basic skills including those of listening, reading, speaking, writing and calculation together with those of observation, analysis and inference which are essentials to the formulation of sound judgement;
2. To ensure the acquisition of the relevant body of knowledge and information which is an essential prerequisite to personal development and the making of positive contribution to the betterment of the society as a whole
3. To create an awareness and understanding of our physical environment and the involving society and cultural processes;
4. To develop the ability for a national utilization of our cultural development;
5. Appreciate the diversity and inter-dependence of all members of the local and the national communities and the need for co-operation for the unity of the country and international understanding; and
6. Inculcate positive attitude and appropriate values of honesty, integrity, hard work, fairness, justice and togetherness for the development of the nation (Denga, 2004)

From the definitions of Guidance Counselling and Social Studies as well as their respective objectives above, the focus of both disciplines is deduced as follows:-

- i. They are visualised as the study of man via the need for necessary adjustment as they interact with socio-physical environment.
- ii They provide a level ground for preparation of younger generation for responsible citizenship.
- iii. They focused on the potential growth of the individual students for future occupational

- development.
- iv. They focused on the promotion of human dignity and values for productivity as pre-requisite for contribution to national development.
 - v. The main attention of both disciplines centres on human behaviour. Thus, inculcate of the right type of skills and virtues into the up-growing generation through a unified, integrated and all-encompassing techniques for survival in this world of mankind remains their concern.

Concept of Citizenship

First and foremost, the concept citizen indicates the generality of people in a state either by birth, registration or nationalization. Ismail cited in Tinja and Tijani (2010) perceived citizenship as the state of being vested with the rights, privileges and duties of a citizen. Accordingly, Ismail cited in Tinja et al (2010) conceived citizenship as dynamic relationship between a citizen and his or her nation. In other words, citizens of a nation is large group of people who live in a country and share common origin, culture, tradition and hold allegiance to common authority. Citizenship is a pre-requisite for full participation of the citizens in the political, social, economy and technological affair of the country for accelerated national growth and development. However, for Nigeria to be fully developed, the country requires effective citizens who place the love of the nation above self. In this line of thought, Lar (1999) perceived effective citizen as:-

one whose life is a good example to his fellow citizens. He does not merely know what is expected of him in the society in which he lives but as far as he can, practices what he knows to be right. He can often be seen helping his fellow citizens without thought of personal gains, and he is anxious at all times to do what can help improving the community in which he lives. Above all, he is honest in word and deed. In his place of work, the good citizen is always punctual and fully dedicated to his duty thus making him highly productive. At home, he is very responsible and takes good care of his family. He mixes very freely with others and corrects them whenever they go wrong. On their parts, the children respect their elders and perform the role expected of them in the society.(p221)

Lar stated further that a good citizen, who is a ruler, makes sure that he is committed to the welfare of his followers and provides them with adequate social services. He also protects his followers from internal and external dangers and has good management of resources under his control. He always preaches peace and unity. As followers, they reciprocate the goodness of their leaders by promptly paying their taxes as and when due. They participate fully in democratic process in order to choose good leaders. They help the police and other security operatives by reporting cases of crime and other dangers in the community and are vigilant against activities that threaten the society. They obey laws of the land and uphold the order of the society. (p221). From the above, it is deduced that effectiveness in citizenship cut across of the total self concept of the individuals; at home, community, society and nation at large.

Hindrances to National Development which Require Collaborative Approach to Citizenship Orientation.

Nigeria of today has completely changed from the Nigeria of yester years in all spheres of her socio-economic and political events. Nigeria has come at a crossroad where nothing seems workable. Certain policies are formulated in all sectors of the economy without yielding positive desired results. The recent happening in the country has clearly shown that peace and security have remained elusive in the society, so the upward trend in poverty and hunger in a nation that has abundant material resources. In this thought pattern, Ezegebe and Okam (2013) reflected that as a nation, our experiences are so sad and painful that there are rational grounds for despair amongst the Nigerian populace. The basics of happiness

for most Nigerians seem not to exist. Even if these existed, Nigeria's leadership and human resources have not considered it sufficiently necessary to choose to source them for securing peace and stability and for emerging and entrenching sustainable security and development.

Discussing the problems of national growth and development, Ikem (2007) identified corruption as a problem, noting that nothing works in the society except if a bribe offered to one whose legitimate duties is to do the job for which he/she is paid. In the same vein, Mezieobi in Ezegbe et al (2013) noted that corruption, embezzlement, squandering of national economy, political naiveté and executive indiscipline are among the behaviours of Nigerian masses. Other manifestations of citizenship behaviour inimical to national growth and development according to Ezegbe et al (2013) include examination malpractice, cultism, ritual killings, falsification of results, disregard to public laws and order, tax evasion, dereliction of duty, "ghost worker" syndrome, inflation of contract terms, illegal trade in drugs, smuggling of contraband materials among others.

In view of the above expositions, Mezieobi in Ezegbe et al (2013) endorsed that for the purpose of nation building and national transformation is to enable citizens and individuals become consummate in the following:- become socially and politically aware, socially integrated into the social milieu. acquire social skills and competences, become socially sensitive and actively participate in their responsibilities for maximum productivity and development all in the interest of Nigeria state. The above reflections demands collaboration of the curriculum contents of Social Studies and Guidance Counselling as unique fields of study, if the task of building effective citizens for accelerated national growth and development is to be accomplished in Nigeria. In this context, the Nigerian schools irrespective of the level of operation need to be proactive and sensitive to citizenship orientation. This assertion therefore calls for effective Social Studies and Guidance and Counselling programmes beginning from the primary education to tertiary educational system to equip the learners with worthwhile values and socially desire attitudes required to make meaningful contributions to socio-economic and political spheres of Nigeria.

Guidance Counselling and Social Studies: Recipe for Desirable Values

Guidance Counselling and Social Studies disciplines helps the students discover and develop their endowed hidden potentials in order to be useful to themselves, their communities and Nigeria as a whole. It therefore follows that these subject areas enhance capacity building of the students for national growth and development. Thus, the curriculum contents of these subject areas promote desirable social values which enable the students to make adjustment to life. Both disciplines unequivocally discourage antisocial behaviours such as hooliganism, vandalism, stealing, drug abuse and addiction and host of others considered inimical to national growth and productivity

Guidance and Counselling gives the individual the opportunity to define, explore, discover and adopt new ways of bringing more satisfying and resourceful life within the social, educational and vocational grouping within which he or she is identified (UNESCO, 2015). In the same analysis, Guidance and Counselling is a programme which is concerned with creating opportunities and suitable environments for the personal, social, educational and vocational growth of the individual through the development of desirable values such hard work, self-esteem, patience, empathy as basis growth of human beings. (Mallum, in North-East Development Commission, 2024). In view of the socio- academic implications of the antisocial behaviours, students are counselled on the need for attitudinal change, being referred to in counselling world as "behaviour modification". This therefore becomes a pre-requisite for not only the development of the individual students but for the benefit of Nigeria as a democratic society.

Similarly, Social Studies as a popular school subject is packaged with relevant value such as self-adjustment, patriotism, honesty, discipline, tolerance, harmonious living, civility, respect for the worth and dignity of labour, service above self, cultivating high spirit of national consciousness, co-operation for national development, Self-reliance, and piety, Justice, productivity, fair-play, sincerity, hard work, orderliness, confidence, diligence, patience, and perseverance, and so on for self and community progress. All the aforementioned are necessary values, the ingredients that the country, Nigeria needs for the realization of her social transformation agenda in its entire ramification.

Assets Intrinsic in Guidance Counselling and Social Studies for Citizenship Development

The challenges of underdevelopment and the urgent needs to make education socially relevant and respond positively to individuals and collective societal demands are largely instrumental to the curriculum development of Guidance Counselling and Social Studies in Nigeria. Guidance Counselling as an applied field of psychology and curriculum design is a core area of the educational support services that facilitates the implementation and the realization of meaningful educational policy in Nigeria. This subject area is packaged with formidable services and techniques such as orientation, appraisal, information, referral, counselling, etc to make teaching and learning more meaningful and goals of education realizable. This, without doubt, constitutes a framework for human resource development which serve as a foundation for national productivity. In this line of thought, the function of Guidance counsellor within the school system as conceived by Tinja & Tijani (2010) is the total development of the individual students to live a self-fulfilled life and contribute to the development of their communities with the understanding of their capacity and weaknesses. According to these scholars, the vision and mission of counselling in Nigeria schools is the development of appropriate socio-academic behaviour that is of inestimable value to the individual learners and the nation at large.

Social Studies education is an instructional design to promote and inculcate values that prepare the individual learners for purposeful life and to be patriotic Nigerians. According to Okobiah in Ezegebe and Okam (2013) Social Studies has the capacities to mobilize the young learners for the purpose of helping them cultivate an understanding that would transform them into citizens with skills, attitudes competencies, moral values and reasoned judgement to effectively live, interact and contribute positively to the economic development of the society. It was against this backdrop that the Federal Republic of Nigeria in the National Policy on Education (2014) regards the teaching of Social Studies as a compulsory core artefact of the curriculum at the levels of primary and secondary education in Nigeria.

Moreover, Guidance counselling and Social Studies provide an avenue for the learners to realize their educational goals which centred on total development of the individual as a base for making personal and collective contributions towards socio-economic and political development of Nigeria. In this Guidance Counselling and Social Studies remain instructional efforts geared towards realization of human dignity and values that will enable the individual citizens contribute meaningfully to national development. Guidance Counselling and Social Studies have undoubtedly emerged as a curriculum design to nursing the potentials and capabilities of the individual students towards functional citizenship through well-articulated curriculum contents and pedagogical strategies. With a view to achieve citizenship development as prerequisite for national transformation in Nigeria Guidance Counselling and Social Studies provide ample opportunity whereby through effective classroom instruction students are counselled to be moral loving and moral doing in a bid to make them productive and useful to themselves and the nation at large.

CONCLUSION

This has perused over the basic potentials of Guidance Counselling and Social Studies education within the frame of partnership to build effective citizens that will support the notion of nation building and national development in Nigeria. The complexity of the socio-economic and political environment in Nigeria without doubt, calls for curriculum contents of Guidance Counselling and Social Studies education. This is so because the Nigeria child of the 21st century according to Kazi (2012) needs an education that will help him or her spot out his or her potentials and develop in the right direction that match with his or her psychological and physical development. In view of this declaration, it is not out of place to present and project the images of Guidance Counselling and Social Studies education as catalyst for the achievement of the above as they sensitize and assist the individual students to choose a career and progress in it for the benefit of themselves, the community and the nation as a whole. However, for Guidance Counselling and Social Studies to function effectively, effort should be made towards solving the following challenges:

1. Insufficient professional counsellors and Social Studies educators is challenge to effective performance in Nigerian schools. This have paved way for social vices such as stealing, bullying, drug abuse, sexual harassment, cultism, hooliganism, lack of respect for constituted authority, examination misconduct and other negative behaviours that constitute threat to human community and national development.
2. Population explosion is also another challenge facing effective implementation og Guidance and Counselling as well as Social Studies education in Nigerian schools
3. Lack of commitment and practical support towards the implementation of counselling programme.
4. Unnecessary existing curriculum gap between Junior and secondary in Social Studies is inimical to the functionality of Social Studies in respect of citizenship development in Nigeria
5. Lack of initiative by the school principals and other heads of schools to establish counselling through the use of Para-counsellor is detrimental to total development of the learners and citizenship development in Nigeria.

Suggestions

In the light of the above deliberations, the following suggestions are made:

1. Government should employ qualified Guidance Counsellors and Social Studies educators to enhance citizenship development for national development in Nigerian
2. Government at all levels in Nigeria should make provision for tackling population explosion through adequate infrastructure development and employment of more teachers. This is necessary to curb varying degree of maladjusted behaviour that hinder students' academic progress
3. Government at all levels should be committed to the implementation counselling programme through provision of adequate office accommodation and facilities such as files and file cabinets, computer among others to Counsellors to facilitate effective counselling service.
4. Government should bridge the curriculum gap in Social Studies between Junior and Senior secondary schools in Nigeria to allow free flow of Social Studies instruction for citizenship development in Nigeria.
5. School principals and other heads of schools should establish counselling programme through the use of Para-counsellor to assist the students and ensure their with a view to foster effective citizenship in Nigeria.

REFERENCES

- Akinola, D. B. (2018). *Principle and Practice of Social Studies Education for Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria*. (Second Edition). Abuja: Chatered Graphic Press.
- Akinola, D. B & Tijani, O. A. (2022). *Character Education as an Antidote forMoral Decadence in a Democratic Nigeria: Implication for Social Studies Education*. www.ingimage.comBAP Benjamin Publishing
- Ashikor, R. M. (2019). Teachers' Perception of the Efficacy of Social StudiesCurriculum in Communal Conflicts Resolution for National Developmentin North-Central Nigeria. A published Ph.D Thesis Submitted to Postgraduate School BenueState University, Makurdi, Nigeria
- Ezegbe, B.N & Okam, C. C. (2013). The Status of Social Studies Education as a Curriculum Design for Generating Civic Society Groups for NationaTransformation in Nigeria. *Nigerain Journal of Social Studies and Civic Education*. 4. (1)12-15.
- Ezekiel, O. O. Adegboyega, I. O & Omoniyi, O. T. (2023). Teachers' Perception ofSocial Studies as a Pedagogical Tool for Citizenship Transformation and Positive Change in New Nigeria. *Journal of African Social Studies* (JASS)4(1) 143-163
- Denga, D. I. (2004). *Guidance and Counselling in School and Working School Seting*. Calabar. Rapid Publishers

- Fakunle, J. O. (2011). *Academic Success and a Happy Career: A Psychological Approach*. badan.Positive.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014). *National Policy on Education*. Abuja. NERDC
- Ikem, K. (2007). Refocusing Citizenship Education in Nigeria: The Role of Educational Agencies. *Journal of Knowledge Review*. 15 (8) 9-10
- Kazi, N.P, (2012). *A Compendium of Economic, Educational, Historical, Political, Religious and Social Issues in Social Studies Education*. Jos. WAIS Printing Press.
- Lar, D. T. (1999). Citizenship Education. In Y.P.S. Ololobou, S. Jacob & J, Ndazhaga (Eds) *Dimension of Social Studies*. Pankshin. Academic Trust Fund.
- North-East Development Commission (2024). *Training Manual for Teachers and School managers for Effective Learning*. Abuja. Government Publisher.
- Odeniyi, O A & Oyedeji, A. O (2014). The Imperative of Counselling as a Tool for Family Security. *The Counsellor*. 33 (2) 1
- Tinja, M..R. & Tijani, O.A. (2010). The Relevance of Qualified Guidance Counsellors in Educational Enterprises: Implication for the Attainment of Millennium Development Goals in Nigeria. An Article Submitted for Publication in *Multidisciplinary Journal of Research Development*.
- Tinja, M. R. (2010). The Role of Guidance and Counselling in Primary Education: Implication for National Productivity. A Paper Presented At the 3rd Zonal Conference (North East) of Colleges of Education Academic Staff.Gombe.27th -29th September.
- Tinja, M. R. (2014). The Role Of Guidance And Counselling In Technology Teacher Education In Nigeria A Chapter Contribution Submitted To The Editor- In Chief of the Journal of Technology Teacher Education Federal College Of Education (Technical) Potiskum